

Previous survey about service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty before revealing various relationships in mobile music application industry

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Abstract : *Based on the existing researches, this paper provides the various dictionaries of important concepts, properties, and relationships among service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty before executing a research to find out what kind of relationship among the above three variables in mobile music application industry. This paper contains the following contents. First, in the introduction, the current state of the mobile music application industry and the purpose of this paper will be described. Second, we will summarize the existing studies on the definition and characteristics of important variables that managers should consider to improve the competitiveness of mobile music application products, ie, service quality, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, and so on. In conclusion, this paper suggests the future research guidelines.*

Keywords: Mobile music application, Service quality, Customer satisfaction, Customer loyalty

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the spread of smart devices such as smart phones, tablet PCs, and wearable devices, and the easy and fast Internet use through mobile communication networks such as LTE-A (Long Term Evolution-Advanced) and Wi-Fi, have contributed to the overall consumer life. It is showing a great ripple effect to change the world, and the platform technology of smart devices is also leading the development of the digital content market. This development has brought about a major change in the accessibility to quickly use desired content through smart devices anytime, anywhere, and has changed the transaction method of digital content to an open structure such as an application store, thereby increasing the amount of digital content that consumers can choose from. It increased explosively, and the quality improved. The role of rich contents such as video and music is becoming more important for both operators and consumers, and related industries are currently competing to gain market advantage in digital music services. The offline music market is showing a gradual decline, but the rapid development of the digital music market is heightening the growth of the music market.

It shows that in the current market environment, a new service strategy and a solution for survival should be sought to have competitiveness compared to other services, and it is a time when not only existing companies but also new operators need to establish a comprehensive business strategy to enhance the competitiveness of their mobile music applications.

In accordance with the growth of the digital music market, research related to digital music services has recently begun in each field. Initially, Hyungwon Choi [1], Jiyeon Yoo [2], Minhye Byun [3] and Kyungchang Lee [4] studied the quality of digital music service, such as the effect of digital (online) music service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. In-Ho Kim [5] and Ah-Hin Shin [6] conducted research by expanding the scope of research on the acceptance of digital music services. Although relatively diverse approaches have been made in relation to digital music services, studies related to mobile-based music services have not been conducted much. Therefore, in this study, before empirically analyzing the factors affecting the service quality of mobile music applications on customer satisfaction and loyalty, a preliminary investigation was conducted on these variables.

II. REVIEW ABOUT PREVIOUS RESEARCHES OF SERVICE QUALITY, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND CUSTOMER LOYALTY

1. SERVICE QUALITY

Table1. Service quality component dimension [7]

10 dimensions	Contents	5 dimensions	Contents
reliability	Consistency of belief in performance (complete service performance, billing accuracy, accurate records, punctuality of promised service)	reliability	same
Reactivity	Motivation and readiness of employees to provide services (timeliness of service, customer mail or phone response, prompt service provision)	Reactivity	same
tangible	Include physical evidence of services (physical facilities, employee appearance, equipment and tools used to provide services, tangible representations of services)	tangible	same
ability	Possess the necessary skills and knowledge to perform the service (knowledge and skills of staff and support personnel, and the organization's research and development capabilities)	certainty	The competence, kindness, credibility, safety, and ability of the company and its employees to communicate it.
kindness	Courtesy, respect, consideration, friendliness of employees (consideration for customers)		
Communication	Provide information in a way that the customer can understand (service description, service cost description, troubleshooting guarantee)		
credibility	Integrity and honesty of the service provider (company name, company reputation, personal characteristics of staff in charge)		
safety	Freedom from risk and suspicion (physical safety, financial security, confidentiality)		
accessibility	Ease of access and contact with the service (acceptable waiting time, convenience of time and place where the service is provided)	empathy	The attention, consideration, and ease of contact that companies and employees give to customers
understand the customer	Efforts to understand customers and their needs (customer specific needs, learning, providing individualized attention, recognizing repeat customers)		

Service quality is defined in various ways, but in many studies, service quality has been defined as the dimension of agreement or incongruity between the expected quality before the service occurs and the quality perceived by the consumer after the service occurs. Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry [7], representative scholars in the field of service quality, define service quality as the degree and direction of mismatch between consumer expectations and perceptions of service. It is said that if the perceived value of receiving and feeling the consumer is high, the service quality is highly evaluated, and Grönroos [8] defined it as the result of comparative evaluation of consumers' perceived service and expected service.

Dodds and Monroe [9] stated that service quality can be largely changed by two approaches: objective quality and subjective quality. Objective quality is a concept to explain the actual technological superiority or excellence between products, and subjective quality is a concept that includes people's subjective reactions to objects [10].

The most representative tool for measuring service quality is the SERVQUAL model developed by Parasuraman et al. [7]. Parasuraman et al. [11] described the factors of service quality such as tangibles, responsiveness, reliability, competence, access, communication, and customer understanding. Parasuraman et al. [7] followed by iterative factor analysis with 97 metrics representing the 10 dimensions of service quality determining factors: the customer), credibility, courtesy, and security. In the study, we redeveloped 5 dimensions and 22 measurement items such as tangibility, empathy, responsiveness, reliability, and certainty by discovering correlations between items. Table 1 below shows the component dimensions of service quality (SERVQUAL) suggested by Parasuraman et al. [11], which is the most used in research on service quality.

Parasuraman et al. [7] presented a GAP model of customer expectations and perceived performance levels, and said that service quality is to evaluate how much service provided to customers satisfies customer expectations. Parasuraman et al. [11] presented a service quality gap model that explains the reason for the gap between customer expectations and awareness, and classified it into five categories.

The first Gap 1 is the difference between customer expectations and management perception, the second Gap 2 is the difference between the management perception and the feasible service level, the third Gap 3 is the difference between the feasible service level and the actual service provided, the fourth Gap 4 is the difference between the service actually provided and external communication. Fifth, Gap 5 is the difference between the service expectation and the service actually perceived. Many companies identify the causes of service quality problems and ways to improve them through this gap model. The upper layer of the model is the customer-related area, and it shows that the customer's service expectations are determined by the customer's personal desire, word of mouth, past experience, and external communication through corporate marketing. It shows that people are influenced by communication [12]. Table 2 shows the types of five GAPs among various elements.

Table 2. GAP Model of Parasuraman et al. [11]

Classification	Type of GAP	Contents
GAP1	GAP between customer expectations and management perception	Disagreement between the business management and the customer about the content of the services provided
GAP2	GAP between management perception and actionable service levels	Service contents that are not practically applicable due to technical difficulties, unrealistic ideas, etc.
GAP3	GAP between executable service level and actual service provided	Side effects in the delivery system, such as employee fatigue and low morale
GAP4	GAP between the service actually provided and the service advertised	GAP of perception by exaggerated advertisements, etc.
GAP5	GAP between expected and recognized services	GAP that occurs when at least one of GAP 1-GAP4 exists

2. CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

The first research on customer satisfaction was developed from marketing research in the early 1980s, and today's customers choose a product or service by judging the value and quality when purchasing a product or service depends on the extent to which the product or service performs compared to expectations before purchase [13].

Oliver [14] stated that the level of customer satisfaction is determined by the difference between the perception of the performance of a product or service after purchase and the expectation of the customer before purchase. The level of satisfaction is higher, and the lower the perception of performance is than the expectation before purchase, the greater the dissatisfaction.

Westbrook [15] defined customer satisfaction as 'a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the evaluation of products, services, retail outlets, and consumer activities'. It was defined as a cumulative and holistic evaluation of experience, and companies with high customer satisfaction showed results such as improved loyalty of existing customers and prevention of churn, reduced cost of creating new customers, reduced price sensitivity, and reduced marketing failure costs.

Park Myung-ho and Cho Hyung-ji [16] classified customer satisfaction into four attributes: cognitive state, an evaluation point of view, emotional response, and emotional response. Customer satisfaction is defined differently depending on whether the focus is on the outcome or the process. In general, the conceptualization of customer satisfaction is somewhat different, but it can be conceptualized by focusing on the perspective and process that can conceptualize customer satisfaction as a result resulting from consumption experience by focusing on the outcome. was defined from a process-oriented point of view and stated that it is a response to the evaluation of the difference between the customer's expectations for a product or service in advance and the actual performance perceived after consumption [5]. Tse et al. [17] defined customer satisfaction as 'the consumer's response to the perceived discrepancy between expectations before consumption and perceived product performance after consumption'.

Combining the above prior studies, customer satisfaction can be said to be a conscious judgment or evaluation of whether a product or service is performed relatively well or whether the product or service is suitable for the purpose of use. In this study, based on previous studies, user satisfaction with mobile music applications was defined as 'the overall satisfaction and relative satisfaction of customers based on the mobile music application experience', and three measurement items consisting of a 5-point Likert scale were used.

Choi [1] stated that satisfaction and dissatisfaction are determined by the degree of inconsistency consumers feel about the service, and this can lead to re-use intention or complaint behavior when viewed through theoretical considerations related to general service quality.

Parasuraman et al. [7] argued that service quality is an antecedent of customer satisfaction, and Cronin and Taylor [18] verified the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction by conducting a survey on a sample spanning several industries. In particular, it was found that service quality in four industries (prevention, dry cleaning, fast food, and banking) had a direct impact on customer satisfaction.

Most studies on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in Korea also conclude that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction. Among them, the dominant conclusion is that the relationship between mobile Internet service quality and customer satisfaction of Kim and Oh [19] also has a positive (+) effect. In a study on the effect of mobile Internet service quality on user satisfaction, Huh [20] found that service quality factors such as sufficiency, playfulness, responsiveness, personalization, perceived contextual usefulness, and design affect customer satisfaction. . Lim [21] said that service quality factors such as sufficiency, personalization, and safety have a positive effect on customer satisfaction in a study on mobile application service quality. Min [22] studied the effect of university library mobile Internet service quality on user satisfaction and reuse intention, and four service quality factors (result quality, fluid interaction quality, contextual interaction quality, service cape) It was found to have a positive effect on customer satisfaction.

3. CUSTOMER LOYALTY

Loyalty is closely related to customer retention, increasing customer profits, and preventing customer churn. Therefore, it is an important factor that enables a company to gain many benefits in a rapidly changing market environment and fierce competition between companies. A focused effort is needed to increase customer loyalty.

Fornell [24] argued that the core of the Internet channel is to induce customer interest as the communication channel between customers and companies becomes the main core through the Internet, and customer loyalty is a key factor in the rapidly changing business environment and fierce competition between companies. It can be said that it is one of the key success factors for a company to survive in the world [5].

Lee [24] defined loyalty as 'a consumer's intention to repurchase a service currently provided in the future based on past experiences and expectations for the future'. He divided the loyalty measurement method into two types, the behavioral approach and the attitude approach. said to be more useful.

Loyalty is divided into three intentions. First, continued use intention is an action that occurs after the acceptance stage and takes place over a long period of time [25]. Second, recommendation intention is defined as the intention of consumers to share their purchasing experience with those around them. In previous studies, customer satisfaction showed a favorable effect on positive word-of-mouth activities such as recommendation [26]. Brand change intention refers to the intention to continuously use the service provided by a specific business operator. Previous studies on

consumer brand change behavior have suggested that it is necessary to understand brand change as a complementary relationship rather than a substitute relationship.

As a result of examining the preceding studies, as shown in Table 3, recent studies are mainly conducted with an attitude-based approach, so this study also borrowed the attitude-based method of measuring loyalty, using a 5-point Likert scale focusing on 'continuous use'. Two configured measurement items were used.

Table 3. Key Approaches to Loyalty Measurement Methods

Classification	Contents	Researchers
Attitudinal approach	Emotional immersion, psychological resistance, and recommendation intention of future consumers such as purchase intention or recommendation intention	Bhattacharjee [25] Lee Moon-gyu [24] Kim In-ho [5]
Behaviorist approach	Behavioral commitment to overall purchases, such as repeat purchases and relative frequency of purchases	Lee Yoo-jae · Ahn Jung-ki [27]

Dick and Basu [28] viewed customer satisfaction as a concept of relationship strength between an individual's relevant attitude and repeated purchases, and Cronin and Taylor [29] found that customer satisfaction significantly affects repurchase intention and also affects the relationship between firms. Therefore, it was said that there is a direct relationship between satisfaction and repurchase intention, and this influence relationship is also applied to the loyalty of the Internet and mobile Internet. Kim Dong-suk [30] studied the effect of satisfaction with use of online and mobile games on game loyalty, and said that satisfaction with use had a significant effect on game loyalty.

Anderson and Srinivasan [31] suggested that customers with high online customer loyalty are more likely to purchase products from that service, and consistently have high repurchase intentions from that service even if they actively promote other services. Therefore, when the customer satisfaction level is high in online and mobile applications, it can be seen that the customer wants to repay the results of various types of products and services provided from the site through voluntary actions [1].

III. CONCLUSION

In this paper, existing studies on service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are summarized. Based on previous researches, the definitions of these variables, their characteristics and interrelationships are included. The purpose of this research provides the various dictionaries of important concepts, properties, and relationships among service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty before executing a research to find out what kind of relationship among the above three variables in mobile music application industry.

That is, in a future research, a research model and hypothesis are developed based on the core variables of about service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, and an expansion study will show what kind of significant relationship among them. For an example, in common sense, the significances of the hypotheses (to be developed) are verified by setting the service quality as an independent variable of customer satisfaction and the customer satisfaction as an independent variable of customer loyalty. In addition, we can also set alternative attractiveness, conversion cost and perceived value as moderators between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. We will apply the hypothesis or research model of such type (to be developed) to mobile music application industry, execute statistical test and draw meaningful implications.

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